

Ambulance Siren Detection using Artificial Intelligence in Urban Scenarios

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Abstract

Traffic density is growing day by day due to the increasing population and affordable prices of cars. It created a void for traffic management systems to cope with traffic congestion and prioritize ambulances. The consequences can be a terrible situation. Emergency vehicles are the most affected in these situations, and inadequate traffic control can put many lives at stake. Ambulances on the road are detected using an acoustic-based Artificial Intelligence system in this article. Emergency vehicle siren and road noise datasets have been developed for ambulance acoustic monitoring. The dataset is developed along with a deep learning (MLP-based) model and trained to use audio monitoring to predict the ambulance presence on the roads. This model achieved 90% accuracy when trained and validated against a developed dataset of only 300 files. With this validated algorithm, researchers can develop a real-time hardware-based model to detect emergency vehicles and make them arrive at the hospital as soon as possible.

Index Terms: Artificial Intelligence, Acoustic Monitoring, Deep Learning, Emergency Vehicle Siren, Multilayer Perceptron.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world's population is significantly increasing as a result, and the number of automobiles on the road is increasing. Therefore, the surge in the traffic density causes severe problems for the traffic administration system to avoid traffic congestion and prioritize emergency automobiles. The presence of emergency vehicles on the road is one of the critical pieces of information for the city administration to clear the path for such vehicles as soon as possible. However, this avalanche in vehicle density leads to a delay in the response of emergency vehicles to reach the accident hotspots. Studies show that when an ambulance arrives at an emergency, it can help reduce pre-hospital mortality by a reasonable number [1].

The most common and significant cause of death in road accidents is delayed hospitalization [2]. A one-minute delay can cause the injured to die on arrival at the hospital. According to a study in [2] and [3], if first aid is not timely, the victim is likely to die while reaching a hospital. Since the reaction time is related to a 6% difference, it is important to reach the hospitals as quickly as possible to provide prompt treatment to the victims. Various improvements in this area have been researched and deployed in urban cities on an experimental basis to overcome this challenge and locate emergency vehicles as early as possible.

In Taiwan, ambulance siren detection is performed using the Longest Common Sequence (LCS) results to compare frequency positions within a frame [4]. The duration of low and high frequencies is 0.4 seconds and 0.6 seconds [5]. The detection of towing vehicles, fire engines, police cars, and ambulances has been proposed [6]. The voice recognition method transforms from the time domain to the frequency domain. While in [7] and [8], Linear Prediction Cepstral Coefficients (LPCC) and Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) are used for sound feature extraction and designing the algorithm. Audio signal sampling and detection comparisons are performed using Artificial Intelligence (AI) based models [9-11].

A microcontroller-based siren detection system uses analog electronics to reduce processing power [12]. It is also a low-cost system, but it is slow in computing power. An automated ambulance detection model is shown here using features extracted from sirens using the Fourier decomposition method [13]. In this article, the authors calculated the MFCC-based features of the siren signal, and then the signal is decomposed in the frequency domain using the Fourier decomposition method.

This paper uses Deep Neural Networks to implement an AI-based audio detection system. The important contributions and outcomes of this research article are listed below:

- One of the paper's most significant contributions is the establishment of a database of ambulance vehicle sirens and real-environment traffic voices. To build a clean and versatile dataset, a total of three hundred samples were captured by employing an emergency vehicle alarm on the streets and recording it in diverse positions.
- Compared to previous siren detection methods, the developed method is quite simple in architecture and requires less computational power. Even the developed model can be programmed on any microcontroller gadget for execution purposes.
- Using Python's Librosa package, a total of 26 features are retrieved from each collected audio sample, together with 21 Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, spectral centroid, spectral bandwidth, roll-off rate, zero-crossing rate, and Chroma_stft. The Deep Neural Network (MLP) classifier is chosen and trained on the data gathered, and it attains a great accuracy rate of 90%.

The remaining article is carried out as follows. The methods for classifying emergency vehicle sounds and database creation are discussed in section II. The test results are presented in Section III, while the paper's summary is presented in Section IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

This paper uses audio classification to implement an efficient deep neural network algorithm for emergency vehicle siren detection. This section is divided into two sub-sections: Database Development and System Software. The first section describes data collection through different techniques, data filtration, and data labeling process. The second section describes the selection of the algorithm, design, and training of the model. A detailed explanation of the sub-sections is given below.

A. Database Development

The audio data collection of emergency vehicle sirens and real-world traffic audio samples, which is discussed below, is one of the most important aspects of this article:

i. Data Collection:

An aggregate of 300 audio clips is gathered in a real-world traffic scenario. An ISO9001: 2015 certified vehicle alarm has been purchased and placed at different crossing points of the town while a recording gadget is utilized to record the ambulance alarms [14]. The recording gadget comprised an auditory microphone (ETS mic) [15], an omnidirectional susceptible mic combined with a laptop utilized for recording gadgets. The ambulance siren audio files are recorded concerning different distance ranges for instance some files have been recorded from 10 meters where the siren is placed (which is stationary) while some from 20, 30, and 40 meters to record all the different intensities of the siren. It makes the dataset more accurate and versatile, having all the audio files of the real world. A total of 150 files are recorded for ambulance siren, while other 150 files are recorded without ambulance siren, walking around the streets to record different natural environment noises. Therefore, a total of three hundred

audio files are gathered and preprocessed. A system architecture is shown in Figure 1 to collect audio files.

Figure 1: A Recording Device for Collecting Data

ii. Data Cleaning and Filtration:

After data collection, another essential step is to clean and discard the distorted audio files. All the collected audio files were manually played and checked. The distorted and low-sampled frequency signals were deleted. A uniform audio range was set, and all the files below 3 seconds and above 15 seconds were cropped. Therefore, a uniform dataset comprises 300 audio files ranging from 3 to 15 seconds. This uniformity helps the system to achieve better accuracy.

iii. Data Labelling:

Data labeling is the crucial step for any automated machine model. Every machine and deep machine model needs classified data to predict the output. The collected audio files are labeled into 1) Ambulance Siren's labels and 2) Traffic Noises without Ambulance Sirens. Each of the classes contains one hundred fifty audio files.

iv. Final Dataset:

The framework opted for data collection and preprocessing is shown in Figure 2. Starting from the raw data collection of audio files of both ambulance siren and road noises, all the audio files were segmented into the 3 to 15 seconds range. Initially, the collected data was in different time durations, to develop a uniform dataset all the files were cropped into particular ranges. Afterward, the collected files were manually heard and the distorted signals were removed from them. Later, low-quality audio signals were upsampled to a fixed and selected sampling frequency which is 48 kHz. All the files below were upsampled at 48 kHz to enhance the data quality and to achieve better accuracies. At last, the dataset was ready for the feature extraction process which is described later in the paper. Summing up the preprocessing steps, Table I provides the details of the utilized audio database.

Figure 2: The Framework used for Dataset Establishment

Table 1: Summary of the Established Database

Parameters	Utilized Database
Ambulance Vehicle Sounds	150
Traffic Sounds	148
No. of Samples	298
Duration (Total)	75 minutes
Audio Samples Length	3-15 seconds
Sampling Frequency	48 kHz

A spectrogram is the visualization of any audio signal, representing different signal parameters. A spectrogram is used to study any signal in amplitude, pitch, and frequency. Before going for the feature extraction process, the time-frequency spectrograms of the ambulance siren and road noises are plotted in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively. The ambulance siren spectrogram also includes the ambient traffic noises. These spectrograms are significant when you are studying any audio signals, their auditory patterns, and their uniqueness. The highest number of frequency components can also be visualized or found by these spectrograms. These figures are used before going for the feature extraction process, just to study the signal.

Figure 3: Traffic Noises Spectrograms, including all the Noises found on Roads (Frequency-HZ Vs Time-Sec)

Figure 4: Emergency Vehicle Siren Spectrograms in Real-Environment (Frequency-HZ Vs Time-Sec)

B. System Architecture

i. Techniques used for Feature Extraction:

The execution of any DNN and ML method is determined by the accuracy with which features are extracted. This technique is the most widely used method for classifying sounds, and it is crucial for decision-making. Linear Prediction Coefficients (LPC) Perceptual Linear Prediction (PLP) and Mel-frequency Cepstral Coefficient (MFCC) are the most common and popular techniques used these days. All these techniques extract relevant information from the audio for recognition purposes. These techniques have been used for a while now according to the suitability of the identification work.

Because of its simplicity and accuracy, the MFCC-based feature extraction approach is one of the most commonly used and employed by scholars. The MFCC is the utmost powerful feature known, with anywhere from 10 to 39 attributes. Each MFCC carries unique signal information such as pitch, power, frequency, and speech attributes, which can assist the system in distinguishing between other audio samples and required signals to make decisions.

The Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficient technique essentially includes windowing the signal, applying the discrete cosine transform, taking the log of the magnitude, and then warping the frequencies on a Mel scale, followed by applying the inverse discrete cosine transform.

Due to the above-mentioned reasons, in this paper, features are extracted using the MFCC technique. all the features, including 21 Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), the roll-off rate, zero-crossing rate, spectral centroid, spectral bandwidth, and Chroma_stft, are extracted. They are gathered in the CSV file (Standard Format). These features are best known and widely used for audio recognition models. Especially MFCCs are the most perceptual scaling feature extraction from the audio signal, which is generally used as input to the AI-based models to produce better results and accuracy than other approaches.

The audio format “WAV” is the sole format supported by the Librosa Library and all the files recorded were in "m4a" format. As a result, all the files were converted to the appropriate format, WAV, before proceeding with feature extraction. A total of 52 characteristics are retrieved from both the classes, 26 each from a single audio file.

ii. The Classifier used for Ambulance Siren Recognition:

For the audio classification of an ambulance siren, a Deep neural network-based MLP model is used. The main idea for choosing this algorithm is the classification model utilized for predicting on nature of applied inputs. The model selection is the main part of any AI application that decides the model performance based on the dataset. The performance of any AI algorithm is calculated through the accuracy; the higher the accuracy, the more model would perform well.

As in this proposed method, we are using MLP, a logistic regression using Feed-Forward ANN to deal with the sequential data, which can use the features extraction to

extract the features from the audio dataset and learn by the proposed model.

MLP model combines one and more neurons used to categorize the separated data. In Figure 5, The block diagram of the Proposed algorithm MLP is presented, which has an input, hidden, and output layer. The Fully connected layers are linked together where Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) and sigmoid function are used.

It improves the nonlinearity of the decision function and the overall network without affecting the receptive fields of the convolution layer. Other nonlinear functions, such as saturated hyperbolic tangent and the sigmoid function, are used to increase nonlinearity. ReLU is superior to other functions in that it allows the neural network to be trained

much faster without sacrificing generalization accuracy. Our model uses an RMSprop optimizer for the learning phase. It eliminates oscillations in the vertical plane from occurring. Consequently, we may be able to increase our learning rate, allowing our algorithm to make more significant horizontal steps and converge more quickly.

In this study, the two label classes are 0 and 1. An MLP model uses 300 data to train sirens and other road noises. To create predictions, the MLP approach is used, and the model has achieved a 96 % accuracy rate the system took around 1.52 minutes to process and train the model on CPU (intel® Xeon(R) Silver 4214 CPU @ 2.20GHz × 48). However, the deep learning model requires more data to increase its performance.

Figure 5: The Proposed Diagram for AI-Based Emergency Vehicle Classification

III. RESULTS

An evaluation of techniques is offered in the findings section. The suggested method detected ambulance sirens in urban traffic with great accuracy. The specifics and outcomes of the whole process, from data curation to training and testing, are provided. There are specific preprocessing processes for audio categorization before feeding into the training model before starting training. To get ready,

Preprocessing methods are utilized as inputs to a neural network. It has the potential to increase the performance of a model. The NN's procedure is to be classified into the appropriate category. The method for preparing a spectrogram will be presented, and we will visualize our audio collection using spectrograms.

The provided audio signals are studied once the dataset has been established and audio has been processed using spectrograms. The data must then be translated into a proper format, like categorical data in the second phase. The entire dataset is turned into structured data to feed the model, specifically discrete labeled groups, as illustrated in Table II. Table II indicates that each sound clip has a label, a class ID, and a designated place for reference during the training of three hundred data samples.

Table II: Emergency Siren and Traffic Sounds Metadata was Generated for the Model's Training

Sound files	Classes	ID	Location
Sound001	Ambulance	0	01
Sound002	Ambulance	0	01
Sound003	Traffic Sounds	1	02
Sound004	Traffic Sounds	1	02

The Metadata of the audio dataset is presented in Table II. Every algorithm in artificial intelligence has the partition data which is appropriate subsets for training and testing. Our algorithm is designed for the classification problem so that the binary data is used heavily for classification deep learning models. Those numbers are binary numbers that are extracted from the audio files using feature extraction methods.

The overall 300 files of audio have been converted into the meaningful information of sequence data, also known as structured data. This structured data is to use for feature extraction purposes. Deep learning has many python

packages that provide audio analysis through the Librosa library for audio analysis in Audio classification for information retrieval. Apart from this, other features like amplitude, frequency w.r.t time analysis, and decoding of the audio data into a 1D array, the default sampling rate is

22 kHz, converted into 48 Khz by upsampling for enhancing the quality, have been considered.

Table III: A Total of 26 Features of Ambulance Siren and Road Noises are extracted from Sound Files in CSV Format

File Name	Chroma_stft	Spectral Centroid	Spectral Bandwidth	Roll-off Rate	Zero-Crossing Rate	MFCC 1	MFCC 2
Ambulance42.wav	0.345168054	0.30885303	1287.145377	1261.699532	2379.211895	0.081082858	74.00363159
Ambulance49.wav	0.386695832	0.263406873	2223.479605	2115.848084	4718.463135	0.122690054	10.77275467
Ambulance188.wav	0.517707944	0.281876475	1393.990435	1586.770873	2898.286321	0.064443735	52.15775681
Road10.wav	0.442203373	0.022000659	2545.346793	2426.47951	4754.28279	0.155189	-270.385
Road118.wav	0.337758154	0.206504658	3470.430019	2706.420324	6899.114051	0.181979	11.29746
Road121.wav	0.440022141	0.173754677	1248.230706	1904.995271	2556.032621	0.020921	-134.684

A total of 26 features are extracted from both the classes (Ambulance Siren and the Road Noises) shown in Table III. These features are unique identities of each sound used by the model for classification purposes. Due to limited space, the above table only shows two of the twenty-one MFCCs here. Extracted features of the audio sound presented in Table III have been labeled as Ambulance and Road Sounds in categorical data. This Data is transformed by using the encoder as 1 and 0. This process is called preprocessing, divided into train and test sets by 80 % for the train set and 20 % for the test set. After diagnosing the preprocessed dataset, it is considered that the Classification problem of this dataset can be resolved by using a deep learning algorithm. A sequential MLP model has input, hidden, and output layers. The model summary is defined in Figure 6.

Figure 7: Trained and Validated Data Percentage Accuracies are shown in this graph

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
dense_12 (Dense)	(None, 100)	2700
activation_12 (Activation)	(None, 100)	0
dropout_9 (Dropout)	(None, 100)	0
dense_13 (Dense)	(None, 200)	20200
activation_13 (Activation)	(None, 200)	0
dropout_10 (Dropout)	(None, 200)	0
dense_14 (Dense)	(None, 100)	20100
activation_14 (Activation)	(None, 100)	0
dropout_11 (Dropout)	(None, 100)	0
dense_15 (Dense)	(None, 2)	202
activation_15 (Activation)	(None, 2)	0

Total params: 43,202
Trainable params: 43,202
Non-trainable params: 0

Figure 6: The no of Layers and Total Parameters of the Model presented for the Multilayer Perceptron Algorithm

Table IV: Research Implementation for the Hardware and Software Requirements

Hardware Environment	
Memory	256 GB
CPU	intel® Xeon(R) Silver 4214 CPU @ 2.20GHz × 48
GPU	NVIDIA Tesla T4

Figure 8 shows the actual vs predicted observations of the accuracies that have been obtained during the process of the training of the model on the Ambulance Dataset in the confusion matrix. Error classes on the off-diagonal and diagonal cells are observed as correct observations.

The Overall Model achieved 90 % accuracy on the limited Data further tested on NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU using python3x programming language in Table 4 in Linux atmosphere and during the training, the computed loss was optimized using Adam as an optimizer.

Figure 8: Predicted and Actual Values of the Accuracies in % showing in Confusion Matrix

Concluding the section, the overall system performance is spot on and reliable but definitely, there is always room for improvement and there are always some limitations. Considering the developed model, the first limitation is that the developed model is not tested in a real-time environment so the accuracy in the real-time scenarios will defiantly be different, and maybe less than that acquired while training because of the size of the dataset that has been curated. The dataset used here is quite small, enhancing the dataset will be the perfect solution when implementing or testing the developed model in real-time.

IV. CONCLUSION

The ambulance siren and traffic noises dataset has been developed in '.wav' formats in this research article. The collected audio signals are first preprocessed before extracting features using Python's Librosa library. Twenty-one Mel-frequency Cepstral Coefficient and the spectral centroid, roll of rate, spectral bandwidth, Chroma_stft, and zero-crossing rate are extracted. A GPU has been utilized for training an MLP model; during the training, the model achieved a 90 % accuracy. The work has focused on designing a dataset and feature extraction process, distinguishing ambulance sound from road noise being the most important. We haven't yet put the data to the test in a real-world environment. We plan to test the data in real-time in the future by recording more audio datasets. The developed model can be used in practice after enhancing the dataset and testing in real-world scenarios. The trained model can be programmed on any microcontroller device and implemented in real-world applications to detect ambulance sirens and optimize the response time. In terms of complexity, the established MLP-model architect is simple enough to run on any micro-processing gadget or any board without a Graphical Processing Unit.

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Authors Contributions

The contribution of the Authors are as follows; Muhammad Usaid's contribution to this study was the concept and correspondence. Muhammad Asif performed the data validation and paper writing. Tabarka Rajab's contribution was administration, and supervision of the project. Munaf Rashid did data collection and methodology. Iqra Hassan performed data compilation.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest between all the authors.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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